

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16938737

Lithofacies and Sedimentological aspect of the Ajali Sandstone at Obinofia Ndiuno Area, Southeastern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Ajali Sandstone was in this study looked at from the sedimentological, and lithofacies points of view. Two representative samples from two different outcrop locations among others were chosen, studied and analyzed in this work. There are the samples from the outcrop of Ajali Sandstone at Ogba cave and outcrop of Ajali Sandstone along Ajali River. The grain size analyses of the representative samples taken from Locations 14 and 3 were carried out and the parameters determined and interpreted. The lithofacies of the Ajali Sandstone was interpreted from the outcrop locations. Ajali Sandstone is of large scale cross-stratification with grains ranging from coarse through medium to fine sizes and the beddings are massive at the base and become thinly laminated upward. It consists of thick friable, poorly sorted sandstone, typically white in colour, but sometimes iron stained. From the study, we conclude that the Ajali Sandstone sediments are partly of beach sands and partly of river sands. The depositional environment of Ajali Sandstone is fluvio-deltaic, continental and a spectrum of environments ranging from marine through paralic to continental.

Keywords: Lithofacies, Sedimentology, Ajali Sandstone, Obinofia Ndiuno, Southeast Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The Ajali Sandstone is one of the three stratigraphic units underlying the study area and it covers more than 70% of the study area (Fig. 1).

This formation consists of thick friable, poorly sorted sandstones, typically white in colour but sometimes iron-stained. A marked banding of coarse and fine layers is displayed. The sand grains and large fragments are subangular, with a sparse cement of white clay. This formation is of large scale cross-stratification with grains ranging from coarse through medium to fine sizes and the beddings are massive at the base and become thinly laminated upward. The formation is underlain by a considerable thickness of red earth, which consists of red, earthy sands, formed by the weathering and ferruginisation of the formation. The formation is well displayed in the study area as found in outcrop of rock exposure within Ogba stream in Ihuezi village Obinofia Ndiuno and along Ajali river bank. On the Udi Plateau, the red earth may be as much as thirty metres thick. North of the Oji River, the higher slopes of the Enugu escarpment consist of the Ajali Formation. Good exposures of the sandstones occurs in the deep gullies incised along the higher slopes of the scarp. The Ajali Sandstone is conformably overlain by the Nsukka Formation (Upper Coal Measures), while the Imo Shale Formation which was deposited during the Paleocene time to lower Eocene time overlies the Nsukka Formation (Fig. 1 and 2).

The depositional environment of the Ajali Sandstone is fluvio-deltaic, continental and a spectrum of environments ranging from marine through paralic to continental. After the deposition of Mamu Formation, there was a retreat to continental condition when a sequence of fresh sandstone of the Ajali Formation was deposited, Kogbe (1976). Rayment (1965) made it clear that the Ajali Sandstone represents a period of active fresh water sedimentation. This can be supported by such features as poor to moderate sorting, cross bedding with dominantly single direction fining upward sequence.

The aim of the study is to describe and define the lithofacies, and sedimentological character of the sediments in order to determine the paleoenvironment of deposition of the Ajali Sandstone.

STUDY AREA

The study area is located within latitudes 6° 15'N to 6° 21'N and longitudes 7° 12'E to 7° 18'E. It is about 121 square kilometers and is within the Anambra basin. The area is underlain by three major formations. These are the cross-bedded, massive Ajali Sandstone (Upper Maestrichian), the Nsukka Formation (Upper Maestrichian to Lower Paleocene) and finally the Imo Shale (Paleocene to Lower Eocene), Figs. 1 and 2.

The mapped area covers part of the western dip slopes of Udi escarpment and eastern section of the Mamu/Anambra plains. The area has a local relief of 350.6m. Physiographically, the area is characterized by a gentle, undulating landscape which generally slopes towards the south-west. The bedrock of the area comprises the sedimentary rocks of upper cretaceous (Rayment 1965). The plain which is the dominant feature in the area is composed of sedimentary rocks which are largely sandstones, shales and clays of cretaceous and tertiary ages (Ofomata, 1975). The study area records a mean annual temperature of 31.2°C. According to Monanu (1975) the climate of the area is 'AM' following Koppen's classification which implies an average rainfall surplus. It has a maximum of 34.3°C and a minimum of 28.3°C. The area records annual rainfall of 1,939mm. It has a maximum of 462.6mm and a minimum of 0.0mm. The vegetation belongs to the rain forest savanna, a greater percentage of the vegetation cover being under grass. The vegetation is being controlled by drainage and the topography. The moderately high ridge area support grassy vegetation with drought resistant deep rooted shrubs that are randomly distributed, whereas in the central low lying area shaly areas, in the river valleys and banks the bush vegetation dominates (Igbozurike, 1975).

Fig. 1: Geologic Map of the Study Area

Scale. Horz. 1:50,000 & Vert. 1: 10,000

Fig. 2: Cross section A – B showing the disposition of the Formation

GEOLOGIC SETTING

The oldest sedimentary basin in southeastern Nigeria (the Benue Trough) originated in early Cretaceous as the failed arms of a rift-rift-rift (RRR) junction associated with the opening of the Atlantic (Burke et al 1970, 1976, Olade, 1975, Wright, 1976, 1961). This view is supported by gravity data (Ajakaiye, 1961). By lower Albian, two stable areas could be distinguished on either side of the Benue Trough, called the Anambra Basin and the Ikpe platforms respectively (Fig.3).Nwachukwu (1972) in his study of tectonic evolution of the southern part of Benue Trough noted that a slight tectonic movement probably took place during the Cenomanian. On the southeastern part of the trough to the northeast is the southwest trending Calabar flank (Ikang Trough) and the Itu High as well as the Eket platform, which persisted with significant changes into the Tertiary. The structural movements in the Benue-Abakaliki Trough which began during Coniacian reached its climax during the Santonian, leading to upliftment to form the Abakaliki Anticlinorium along the NE-SW axis (Fig. 3). The structural inversion was accompanied by the formation of depression on the either flank- the smaller Afikpo synclines on the northeast. Thus there existed three sedimentary basins from the Campanian to the Paleocene. The Anambra Basin and the Afikpo Syncline was (separated by the Abakaliki High and the Ikang Trough (Short and Stauble 1967, and Murat , 1972).

The stratigraphy and sedimentological history of the Benue Trough are documented by Peters, 1978, Wright 1967, Hoque and Nwajide, 1985. The major control of sedimentation resulted from the World wide eustatic changes in sea level and basin tectonic, (Table 1) gives the correlatable stratigraphic sequence in the three depositional basins of the southeastern Nigeria. Sedimentation in the Anambra Basin commenced with the Campano - Maestrichian marine and paralic shales of the Enugu and Nkporo Formations. These basal units are overlain successively by the coal bearing Mamu Formation (Lower Coal Measures), the conspicuously cross-bedded Ajali Sandstones (Middle Coal Measures), and the coal bearing Nsukka Formation (Upper Coal Measures).

Fig.3: Part of Southern Nigeria showing relief forms and principal fold axes

TABLE 1: STRATIGRAPHIC SEQUENCE OF THE FORMATION IN SOUTH EASTERN NIGRIA SEDIMENTARY BASIN WITH THE POSITION OF FORMATION ENCOUNTERED IN THE STUDY AREA, THEIR APPROX. THICKNESS AND DEPOSITIONAL CYCLE. Adapted from Reyment 1965

Period	Age	Formation Name	Depositional Cycle	Maximum Thickness (Approx) M
Tertiary	Miocene- Pleistocene	Benin Formation		?
		Agbada Formation		?
		Akata Formation		?
	Oligocene	Ogwashi-Asaba Formation		
	Eocene	Nanka sand/Ameki Formation	Regression	1,600
Cretaceous	Paleocene	Imo Shale	Transgression (Marine)	1,334 +
	Maestrichtian	Nsukka	Transgression	368
		Ajali		368
		Mamu		434
	Campanian	Owelli/Enugu	Transgression	866
Senonian	Nkporo Agwu-Ndeaboh Shales	Regression	500 + 668	
Santonian Coniacian				
	Turonian	Ezeaku Shale	Transgression	1,688
	Cenomanian	Odukpani Formation	Regression	
	Albian	Asu River Group	Transgression	2,000 +

A south return to transgressive sedimentation during the Tertiary led to the deposition of the blue and dark grey fossiliferous Imo Shale (Paleocene) and the hetresolithic Ameki/Nanka/Nsugbe Formations on top of the maestrichtian sequence. The subsequent regressive cycle was marked by the parallitic Ogwashi-Asaba Formations (Mid Eocene) followed by the sediments of the Niger Delta.

METHODOLOGY

A reconnaissance survey was first carried out to observe the general physiographic features in the area in order select localities of interest. After this, detailed field work was carried out which involved the study of the lithologic sequences and units, the dip and strike measurements. Samples were collected at various stations/locations and coded according to their locations of retrieval. The samples used for the grain size analysis were taken from an outcops of Ajali Sandstone at Ogba cave and along the Ajali River bank . The colour variations in the lithologies found along road cuts, stream channels, excavation sites and gullies were taken note of. The collected samples were subjected to grain size analyses at the laboratory using the automatic sieve shaker.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Ajali Sandstone consists of thick friable, poorly sorted sandstone, typically white in colour, but sometimes iron-stained. The angle of inclination of the foreset laminae with the underlying major bedding planes ranges up to 20⁰.

From the statistical sieve analysis of the two representative samples, it is inferred that the formation is poorly sorted (1.00 – 2.00) (Tables 2, Figs. 4, 4a, 5 and 5b). The calculated skewness ranges between 0.10

to 0.30 (positively skewed) for sample 1 and between 0.10 to 0.30(positively skewed) for sample 3 (Folk and Ward). Based on the above result of (sorting and skewness) the Ajali Sandstone must have been deposited quickly as shown by its poorly sorted nature, must have been reworked in the depositional environment (see also Figs. 4b and 5b).

From the skewness analysis we can still make some observations based on the depositional process of the Ajali Sandstone. Beach sand for example tend to have – negative number in skewness, since the fine components have been removed by wave action, while the river sands are positively skewed, since much of the silt and clay are not removed (Maurice E.T. 1988). From the above, we can conclude that the Ajali Sandstone sediments are partly of beach sands and partly of river sands.

Table 2: Results of the Granulometric Analysis of Ajali Sandstone Sediments

Sample Location	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Description
Location 1	0.78	1.38	0.3	1.01	Coarse sand, Poorly sorted, Positively skewed and Mesokurtic
Location 3	1.28	1.24	0.12	1.16	Medium sand, Poorly sorted, Positively skewed and Leptokurtic

Fig.4: Particle Size Distribution of Ajali Sandstone Location 14

Fig.4a: Cumulative % of Ajali Sandstone Location 14

Fig.4b: Weight % Retained (Histogram) of Ajali Sandstone Location 14

Fig.5: Particle Size Distribution of Ajali Sandstone Location 3

Fig.5a: Cumulative Weight % of Ajali Sandstone Location 3.

Fig.5b: Weight % Retained (Histogram) Ajali Sandstone Location 3.

The Lithofacies analyses of the Ajali Sandstone

The nature of the outcrop in location 14 is a rock exposure within Ogba stream in Ihuezi village Obinofia Ndiuno. The exposure is about 330 metres thick (Fig.6 and 7). It consists of gravel and pebble brownish sandstone of about 50 metres thick and this is underlain by fairly weathered false bedded fine grained sandstone of about 260 metres thick. The base is of whitish medium to coarse sandstone of 20 metres thick ..

The nature of the outcrop in location 3 is a rock exposure along Ajali River in Okpueze Umumba. The exposure is about 5.4 metres thick. It consists of top lateritic brownish soil of 1.4 metres thick. This is underlain by fine to coarse whitish sandstone of about 4 metres thick

Fig. 6: Outcrop section of the Ajali Sandstone at Ogba Cave Location 14.

Fig. 7: Outcrop section of Ajali Sandstone along Ajali River bank location 3.

PALEOENVIRONMENT OF AJALI SANDSTONE

The depositional environment of the Ajali Sandstone is fluvio-deltaic, continental and a spectrum of environments from marine through paralic to continental. After the deposition of Mamu Formation, there was a retreat to continental condition when a sequence of the Ajali Formation was deposited, (Kogbe (1976). From the fining upward sequence of the sediments deposited we can infer that it is of transgressive phase which suggests deposition in fluvio-continental environment followed by fluctuation, channel migration and basin subsidence.

Reyment (1965) made it known that the Ajali Sandstone represents a period of active fresh water sedimentation. This can be supported by such features as poor to moderate sorting, cross bedding with dominantly single direction fining upward sequence.

CONCLUSION

The Ajali Sandstone occupies more than 70% of the study area. The lithofacies and sedimentological aspects of the formation were studied. The formation is of large scale stratification with grains ranging from coarse through medium to fine size. The Ajali Sandstone consists of thick friable, poorly sorted sandstone, typically white in colour but iron stained. Two representative samples from locations 14 and 3 were studied and analyzed. From the lithofacies analysis of the outcrop section at location 14 we observed a gravel and pebble reddish brown sandstone at the top which is underlain by a fairly weathered false bedded sandstone and with a whitish medium to coarse sandstone at the base. Also at the location 3, we observed a top lateritic brownish soil which is underlain by fine to coarse whitish sandstone. From the statistical sieve analysis of the representative samples, it is inferred that the formation is poorly sorted. From the skewness data, sample locations 14 and 3 are positively skewed. From the above we conclude that the Ajali Sandstone sediments are partly of beach sands and partly of river sands. The depositional environment of the Ajali Sandstone is fluvio-deltaic, continental and a spectrum of environments ranging from marine through paralic to continental. From the fining upward sequence of the sediments deposited, we can infer that it is of transgressive phase which suggests deposition in fluvio continental environment followed by fluctuation, channel migration and basin subsidence.

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